

INVESTIGATION OF THE OIL SYSTEM IN HIGHWAY PIPELINES

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Abstract

The separation of fluid and mechanical solid particles from transported gas and their collapse on the relief cavity of the pipeline lead to the breakdown of flow regularity and the service life decrease of pipeline and technological equipment. Moreover, the condensate and mechanical solid particles contained in the gas supplied to the enterprises of industrial processing create difficulties during normal operation of technological equipment.

For the separation and gathering of condensate and solid mechanical particles in gas transportation based on specific weight and mechanical energy, installation of tank for condensate gathering at the beginning and end of the pipeline alongside flow direction and the change of gas flow direction by means of a tee fixed before the tank are offered.

Keywords: pipeline, condensate, mechanical solid particles, filter, condensate storage capacity, density, mechanical, kinetic and potential energy.

The results of the observations and investigations undertaken indicate that vertical gravity separators are used to separate the gas and condensate from the well-extracted gas-condensate. Aerodynamic forces prevent mechanical solid particles with a size of several micrometers from sinking to the bottom of the separator despite the repeated separation of gas; instead, they travel along with the gas flow. As a result, the quantity of mechanical solid particles, such as moisture and dust, that are present in the gas that is provided to the user through the main gas pipeline occasionally exceeds the standard. In order to capture moisture and mechanical solid particles, filter separators are typically positioned at the end of the belt, and their performance is continuously tracked. There is a lot of labor involved in cleaning and replacing the separator's filter throughout the course of the day, and there is also a risk of environmental pollution and gas emissions up to the separator's nominal volume at operating pressure.

A portion of mechanical solid and condensate particles that have been separated during the transit of gas gather in depressions along the pipeline's terrain. As a result, the gas pipeline's throughput declines, hydraulic resistance pressure losses rise, flow irregularities, vibrations, and hydraulic shocks happen, and the pipeline's inner surface experiences increased corrosion and erosion. As a result, the gas pipeline is less durable and has a shorter lifespan. The operation of control measuring devices, automatic adjustment devices, and compressive compressors are negatively impacted by mechanical solid and condensate particles, which also increases errors in gas consumption measuring devices and decreases their reliability and durability [1]. Condensate and mechanical solid particles found in the gas supplied to major industrial

firms make it more difficult to regulate technological operations and raise the possibility of equipment failure before its time.

Research have revealed that compared to the end of the pipeline, the pressure of the gas flow is higher and the speed is lower near the entrance. In the depression zones of the pipelines, a portion of the condensate and solid particles are thus separated and gathered. Condensate and mechanical solid particles in the pipeline are removed more effectively because of the increased gas flow velocity near the belt's end. As the pressure gradually decreases throughout the pipeline's length, the liquid phase gradually evaporates, which causes the gas phase in the gas pipeline to become moist. A portion of the liquid phase in the gas pipeline transitions into the gas phase due to the rise in moisture content of gases under low pressure.

As a result of research, it was determined that As a result of research, it was determined that C2; C3; C4; C5; found in gases found in gases. In general, condensation occurs when the sum of the densities of the components is $\sum x > 1$, and condensation does not occur when $\sum x < 1$ [2].

Sour gases (H₂S and CO₂) in the gas significantly affect its thermodynamic parameters and ensure the maintenance of humidity in the gas phase [3].

According to the normative document "Main Pipeline Design Norms", it is recommended to install condensate collecting capacities in depressions of gas pipelines in order to check the presence of condensate and release it. In this instance, the number of condensate storage capacities likewise grows as a result of the pipeline's increased length. Only the liquid and solid particles that have settled at the bottom of the pipe are collected in the condensate storage tanks during

installation; the majority of the liquid and solid particles continue to move with the gas flow due to the influence of aerodynamic forces.

Liquid and solid particles of mass m along the belt move with the gas flow at a speed v and have a kinetic energy of $mv^2/2$ [3]. Under normal conditions, the mass of the liquid (condensate) is $\approx 760 \text{ kg/m}^3$, the mass of mechanical solid particles is $\approx 1200 \text{ kg/m}^3$, and the mass of the gas component is $\approx 0.8 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

The gas density at a given working pressure and temperature is determined by the following formula [4]:

$$\rho_{work} = \frac{\rho_0 z_n T_n p_{work}}{p_n z_{work} T_{work}}$$

Right here ρ_0 – the density of a gas under normal conditions, kg/m^3 ; p_{work} – working pressure, MPa; T_{work} – working temperature, K; T_n – normal temperature, 293 K; p_n – normal pressure, $p_n = 0.102$ MPa; z_n, z_{work} – are gas compressibility coefficients under normal and working conditions. The pressure of gas transported by main pipelines can be from 1.0 MPa to 9.0 MPa. When the working pressure is 1.0 MPa, the gas density is $\approx 8 \text{ kg/m}^3$; At 9.0 MPa, it is $\approx 70 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

In a short amount of time, the particles of the gas component, mechanical solid, and condensate all move through the pipeline's cross section at roughly the same rates, while having different masses, according to a comparison of the kinetic energy of the particles. The kinetic energy of mechanical solid and condensate particles will be greater than the kinetic energy of gas components because their mass is ten times more than that of gas components. Due to the differences in

kinetic energy brought on by the weight of the particles, it is necessary to install a condensate collection capacity in the direction of the movement flow as a continuation of the pipeline in order to separate and collect the mechanical solids and condensate particles from the gas flow. By adding a tee and an end elbow to the belt before the cap, the gas flow is continued while the direction of the flow is changed. In this situation, the condensate storage capacity serves as a trap for both condensate and mechanical solids particles. Thus, mechanical solid particles of m_b mass and condensate particles of m_k mass moving with α acceleration will be separated from the gas components by $m_b a$ and $m_k a$ forces and thrown into the condensate storage capacity, and will sink to the bottom of the capacity due to $m_b g$ and $m_k g$ gravities. Aerodynamic forces are avoided and the separation of settled mechanical solid and condensate particles is guaranteed because the gas flow inside the tank is not moving.

The major gas pipeline's proposed technological layout is shown in Figure 1. Condensate collection capacity were placed in the beginning and end portions of the pipeline as a continuation of the pipeline in order to improve the quality indicators of the gas provided to the consumer. By adding a tee and then an elbow to the belt before the tanks, the gas flow's direction was adjusted. Discharge and intake chambers should be constructed after the condensate storage capacity at the beginning of the pipeline and before the condensate storage capacity at the end of the pipeline in order to remove accumulated condensate and mechanical particles in the interim segment. At various intervals, releasing the arse from the start should be done to clean the interior of the belt.

Figure 1. The proposed technological scheme of the gas pipeline:

GPB – the beginning of the gas pipeline; GPE – the end of the gas pipeline; CSC – condensate storage capacity; DC – drain capacity; RC – release chamber; EC – ersingabulu camera; DL – discharge line; DP – drilling pipe.

Figure 2. The scheme of the capacitor:

A – gas inlet; B – gas outlet; C – outlet of condensate (80 mm); Ч – reserve outlet of condensate (150 mm); D – reserve line (80 mm); E – output for the level indicator (80mm); A – protective valve for pressure relief of the tank.

Figure 2 shows the diagram of the condenser capacity. In accordance with the requirements of the normative document "Safety rules for the operation of main gas pipelines", control-measuring devices, protective valves, appropriate connectors for emptying the capacity and removing condensate from the capacity are designed on the capacity. Due to gas pressure, condensate that has accumulated in the condensate storage capacity is collected and transferred to the prescribed location for disposal in a tank truck intended to transport oil products. Safety regulations as outlined in regulatory documents must be adhered to when collecting and transporting condensate from the tank. The tank's condensate must be drained throughout the day and in the absence of wind.

The result

1. 1. Condensate collection capacities must be installed at the beginning and end of pipelines in order to separate and collect mechanical solids and condensate particles from the gas stream due to differences in kinetic energy from the gas flow in order

to improve the quality indicators of the gas supplied to the consumer.

2. The belt is extended by adding a triple, followed by an elbow, in front of the tanks. This changes the direction of the gas flow to the condensate collecting tank, causing mechanical solid and condensate particles to be separated from the gas flow and thrown into the tank due to their differences.

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